

Lanchester Combat Model with One-sided Information

Charles Li*

Department of Mathematics, Mercy University, Dobbs Ferry, NY, USA

Abstract

The Lanchester combat model (Lanchester square law) is analyzed from the perspective of limited information from just one side of the battle. We tackle this matter theoretically and then test it in practice with real combat data from the Battle of Iwo Jima. A recurrence relation is developed which theoretically enables the battle outcome and intensity of the battle to be deduced from knowing one side's force levels at three moments in time, without any knowledge of the other side's force levels. Furthermore, it is not necessary to know the attrition rates as is usual with the Lanchester model. This analysis with limited one-sided information can be thought of as a formal mathematical model exploring the effects of a fog of war on the Lanchester combat model.

Our one-sided combat model is tested with data from the Battle of Iwo Jima

*cli2@mercy.edu or charlesli.jianwei@gmail.com

and is shown to be successful at making short-term predictions of friendly force levels, but not long-term predictions.

1 INTRODUCTION

The Lanchester combat model (Lanchester square law) serves as the foundation for military planning in the US military as well as other militaries around the world. This paper will explore a sort of fog of war on the Lanchester combat model in the sense that information about enemy force levels will not be known and we will only rely on information about friendly forces to draw our conclusions. We will show that the outcome of the battle as well as the intensity of the battle can be obtained from using only one-sided attrition information at three moments in time.

Lanchester and Osipov independently created and analyzed the system of differential equations that led to the Lanchester square law for modern warfare with aimed fire. Suppose the two sides of the battle are X and Y with force levels $x(t)$ and $y(t)$, respectively, at time t . Then the Lanchester combat model is governed by the following system of differential equations, i.e. the Lanchester equations:

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = -\beta y \quad , \quad \frac{dy}{dt} = -\alpha x \quad (1)$$

where α is the attrition rate describing how fast X forces can eliminate Y forces, and β is the attrition rate describing how fast Y forces can eliminate X forces. The attrition rates are assumed to be constants.

Dividing the two equations in (1) to get rid of dt results in a differential equation

in x and y :

$$\frac{dy}{dx} = \frac{\alpha x}{\beta y} \quad (2)$$

Solving this differential equation leads to the well-known Lanchester square law:

$$\alpha x^2 - \beta y^2 = \text{constant} \quad (3)$$

This can be interpreted to say the fighting strength of each side can be measured as the product of the attrition rate that it can inflict on the other side times the force level squared. Whichever side has the higher fighting strength will win the battle of attrition in this deterministic combat model.

Now suppose we don't have complete knowledge of the situation as is often the case in real warfare, i.e. there exists a fog of war. Assume both attrition rates α and β are unknown at the outset of battle. Assume each side does not know the force levels of the other side. Assume the dynamics of combat are governed by the Lanchester equations (1).

Without loss of generality, we will look at the battle from the X perspective. The commander of the X forces is able to know his own force levels at various times. We will measure $x(t)$ at three different times t and will use this limited one-sided information to deduce the course of the battle.

In this paper, we will first lay a theoretical foundation, then we will test our one-sided combat model with real data from the Battle of Iwo Jima. Our model will be shown to be useful in making short-term predictions about friendly force levels, but not long-term predictions.

2 RECURRENCE RELATION

Our main technical tool will be a recurrence relation that we will set up in this section.

Lemma 2.1. Let $t_a < t_b$ be two moments in time. Let $x_a = x(t_a)$ and $x_b = x(t_b)$.

Let $I = \sqrt{\alpha\beta}$. Then the X force level at time t is given by:

$$x(t) = \frac{x_b e^{-It_a} - x_a e^{-It_b}}{e^{I(t_b-t_a)} - e^{-I(t_b-t_a)}} e^{It} + \frac{x_a e^{It_b} - x_b e^{It_a}}{e^{I(t_b-t_a)} - e^{-I(t_b-t_a)}} e^{-It} \quad (4)$$

Proof. Start with the Lanchester equations (1) and differentiate $\frac{dx}{dt}$ to get the second derivative, then substitute $\frac{dy}{dt} = -\alpha x$:

$$\frac{d^2x}{dt^2} = -\beta \frac{dy}{dt} = \alpha\beta x \quad (5)$$

This second order differential equation in x has characteristic equation $s^2 - \alpha\beta = 0$ with roots $s = \pm\sqrt{\alpha\beta} = \pm I$. Thus, we have the general solution:

$$x(t) = k_1 e^{It} + k_2 e^{-It} \quad (6)$$

Plugging $t = t_a$ and $t = t_b$ we get the following:

$$x_a = k_1 e^{It_a} + k_2 e^{-It_a} \quad , \quad x_b = k_1 e^{It_b} + k_2 e^{-It_b} \quad (7)$$

which in the matrix form $x = Ak$ is:

$$\begin{bmatrix} x_a \\ x_b \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} e^{It_a} & e^{-It_a} \\ e^{It_b} & e^{-It_b} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} k_1 \\ k_2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

The inverse matrix A^{-1} is given by:

$$A^{-1} = \frac{1}{e^{It_a}e^{-It_b} - e^{-It_a}e^{It_b}} \begin{bmatrix} e^{-It_b} & -e^{-It_a} \\ -e^{It_b} & e^{It_a} \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

$$A^{-1} = -\frac{1}{e^{I(t_b-t_a)} - e^{-I(t_b-t_a)}} \begin{bmatrix} e^{-It_b} & -e^{-It_a} \\ -e^{It_b} & e^{It_a} \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

Substituting A^{-1} into the matrix equation $k = A^{-1}x$, then substituting for k_1 and k_2 in (6) completes the proof. \square

Definition. Suppose we measure X force levels at times $t = 0$ and $t = T$ for some $T > 0$. We will work with multiples of T , so let's set up the following notation which will be used throughout the paper:

$$t_k = kT \quad , \quad x_k = x(t_k) \quad \text{for } k \geq 0 \quad (11)$$

Theorem 2.2. (Recurrence Relation) Working with multiples of time T , the X force

levels satisfy the following recurrence relation:

$$x_k = \frac{x_{k-1}(x_{k-1} + x_{k-3})}{x_{k-2}} - x_{k-2} \quad \text{for } k \geq 3 \quad (12)$$

Proof. Starting from equation (4), plug $t_a = t_{k-1}$ and $t_b = t_k$. This was chosen so that $t_b - t_a = t_k - t_{k-1} = T$. We get:

$$x(t) = \frac{x_k e^{-I(k-1)T} - x_{k-1} e^{-IkT}}{e^{IT} - e^{-IT}} e^{It} + \frac{x_{k-1} e^{IkT} - x_k e^{I(k-1)T}}{e^{IT} - e^{-IT}} e^{-It} \quad (13)$$

Plugging $t = t_{k+1}$ yields:

$$x_{k+1} = \frac{x_k e^{-I(k-1)T} - x_{k-1} e^{-IkT}}{e^{IT} - e^{-IT}} e^{I(k+1)T} + \frac{x_{k-1} e^{IkT} - x_k e^{I(k-1)T}}{e^{IT} - e^{-IT}} e^{-I(k+1)T} \quad (14)$$

$$x_{k+1} = \frac{x_k e^{2IT} - x_{k-1} e^{IT} + x_{k-1} e^{-IT} - x_k e^{-2IT}}{e^{IT} - e^{-IT}} \quad (15)$$

We can rewrite in terms of the hyperbolic sine function as follows:

$$x_{k+1} = \frac{x_k \sinh 2IT - x_{k-1} \sinh IT}{\sinh IT} \quad (16)$$

Next, starting from equation (4), plug $t_a = t_{k-2}$ and $t_b = t_{k-1}$ so that once again $t_b - t_a = T$.

$$x(t) = \frac{x_{k-1} e^{-I(k-2)T} - x_{k-2} e^{-I(k-1)T}}{e^{IT} - e^{-IT}} e^{It} + \frac{x_{k-2} e^{I(k-1)T} - x_{k-1} e^{I(k-2)T}}{e^{IT} - e^{-IT}} e^{-It} \quad (17)$$

Plugging $t = t_{k+1}$ and simplifying yields:

$$x_{k+1} = \frac{x_{k-1}e^{3IT} - x_{k-2}e^{2IT} + x_{k-2}e^{-2IT} - x_{k-1}e^{-3IT}}{e^{IT} - e^{-IT}} \quad (18)$$

Rewriting in terms of the hyperbolic sine function:

$$x_{k+1} = \frac{x_{k-1} \sinh 3IT - x_{k-2} \sinh 2IT}{\sinh IT} \quad (19)$$

Setting (16) and (19) equal and cancelling out the $\sinh IT$ yields:

$$x_k \sinh 2IT - x_{k-1} \sinh IT = x_{k-1} \sinh 3IT - x_{k-2} \sinh 2IT \quad (20)$$

It follows from a little bit of algebra that:

$$\frac{x_k + x_{k-2}}{x_{k-1}} = \frac{\sinh 3IT + \sinh IT}{\sinh 2IT} \quad \text{for } k \geq 2 \quad (21)$$

Notice the right hand side of equation (21) is a constant, thus the form on the left hand side is an invariant as k varies. The proof is complete by noting the following equation and doing algebra:

$$\frac{x_k + x_{k-2}}{x_{k-1}} = \frac{x_{k-1} + x_{k-3}}{x_{k-2}} \quad \text{for } k \geq 3 \quad (22)$$

□

Corollary 2.3. (Invariant Form) We have the following invariant form for $k \geq 2$:

$$\frac{x_k + x_{k-2}}{x_{k-1}} = \frac{\sinh 3IT + \sinh IT}{\sinh 2IT} \quad (23)$$

Hence we also have:

$$\frac{x_2 + x_0}{x_1} = \frac{x_3 + x_1}{x_2} = \frac{x_4 + x_2}{x_3} = \frac{x_5 + x_3}{x_4} = \dots \quad (24)$$

Proof. This result was demonstrated in the proof of Theorem 2.2. □

3 THEORETICAL CONSIDERATIONS

We use the main recurrence relation and invariant form to develop some results that build towards a “one-sided Lanchester theory”.

3.1 Battle Termination

Most battles are not fought to annihilation, so this section is mostly theoretical. Assuming the battle is fought to the annihilation of one or both sides, then the Lanchester combat model ends in three potential outcomes: 1) X wins and Y loses, 2) Y wins and X loses, or 3) X and Y are mutually annihilated at the same time. The winner will have a positive number of survivors while the loser’s forces are reduced to 0. In the case of mutual annihilation, both side’s forces are reduced to 0.

Let t_e be the battle ending time when the annihilation of at least one side’s forces is achieved. Let $x_e = x(t_e)$ and $y_e = y(t_e)$. The three respective potential outcomes

are: 1) $x_e > 0$ and $y_e = 0$, 2) $y_e > 0$ and $x_e = 0$, and 3) $x_e = y_e = 0$.

In the formal math, we can still use the equations to describe the force levels for times after t_e even though the real world interpretations of the math would be nonsensical. From X 's perspective: 1) if X wins, then $x(t)$ will start increasing for $t > t_e$ since we would be plugging in negative values of y in the differential equation (1), 2) if X loses, then $x(t) < 0$ for $t > t_e$, and 3) $x(t) = 0$ for $t > t_e$ if X and Y are mutually annihilated.

Using the recurrence relation in Theorem 2.2, we can find the X force levels over time in multiples of T without knowing Y force levels $y(t)$ and without knowing the attrition rates α and β . We just need 3 data points to start off the recurrence. Assume x_0 , x_1 and x_2 are known, then x_k can be calculated for $k \geq 3$.

The X and Y force levels are undergoing attrition in the Lanchester combat model and one of the three battle outcomes will be reached even if we are just working with limited one-sided information about the battle. There exists an integer $N > 0$ such that $t_N = NT > t_e$ and one of the three battle outcome behaviors for X will be exhibited if we compute $x_N = x(t_N)$ for N large enough. Thus, we can figure out the battle outcome in a finite number of steps by using the recurrence relation in Theorem 2.2 with just one-sided information.

The discussion above is summarized in the following theorem.

Theorem 3.1. (Battle Outcome) Let t_e be the battle ending time. Given x_0 , x_1 and x_2 . There exists an integer $N > 0$ such that $t_N > t_e$ and one of three behaviors in x_k will occur:

1. x_k is an increasing function for $k \geq N$ (X wins, Y loses)

- 2. $x_k < 0$ for $k \geq N$ (Y wins, X loses)
- 3. $x_k = 0$ for $k \geq N$ (X and Y mutually annihilated)

3.2 Generating Function

The recurrence relation and the invariant form from which it came are crucial in this paper. In this section we find an associated generating function for completeness' sake. Techniques from “generatingfunctionology” Wilf (2006) can be used to work with the x_k without necessarily computing all values of x_k sequentially.

Let $f(s) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} x_k s^k$ be a formal power series in variable s which contain the sequence of x_k as coefficients, i.e. a generating function for the sequence of x_k .

Let $c = \frac{\sinh 3IT + \sinh IT}{\sinh 2IT} = \frac{x_2 + x_0}{x_1}$, i.e. the constant from the invariant form (Corollary 2.3), which we in theory know since x_0 , x_1 and x_2 are known in our one-sided information scenario.

Theorem 3.2. A generating function f for the sequence x_k is given by:

$$f(s) = \frac{x_0 + (x_1 - cx_0)s}{1 - cs + s^2} \tag{25}$$

Proof. By Corollary 2.3, we have:

$$\frac{x_k + x_{k-2}}{x_{k-1}} = c \quad \text{for } k \geq 2 \tag{26}$$

$$x_k + x_{k-2} = cx_{k-1} \tag{27}$$

$$x_k = cx_{k-1} - x_{k-2} \tag{28}$$

Preparing the generating function f to work with the recurrence in (28), we have:

$$sf = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} x_k s^{k+1} = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} x_{k-1} s^k = x_0 s + \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} x_{k-1} s^k \quad (29)$$

$$s^2 f = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} x_k s^{k+2} = \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} x_{k-2} s^k \quad (30)$$

Start with (28), multiply by s^k and sum from $k = 2$ to ∞ :

$$\sum_{k=2}^{\infty} x_k s^k = \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} c x_{k-1} s^k - \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} x_{k-2} s^k \quad (31)$$

Add $x_0 + x_1 s$ to both sides:

$$x_0 + x_1 s + \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} x_k s^k = x_0 + x_1 s + c \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} x_{k-1} s^k - s^2 f \quad (32)$$

$$\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} x_k s^k = x_0 + x_1 s + c(s f - x_0 s) - s^2 f \quad (33)$$

$$f = x_0 + x_1 s + c s f - c x_0 s - s^2 f \quad (34)$$

$$f - c s f + s^2 f = x_0 + x_1 s - c x_0 s \quad (35)$$

$$f = \frac{x_0 + (x_1 - c x_0) s}{1 - c s + s^2} \quad (36)$$

□

3.3 Intensity of the Battle

The geometric mean of the two attrition rates, $I = \sqrt{\alpha\beta}$, can be thought of as a measure of the intensity of the battle. In this section we demonstrate how to find I given our limited one-sided information, working with only x_0 , x_1 and x_2 as a starting point due to the fog of war.

Recall that the constant $c = \frac{\sinh 3IT + \sinh IT}{\sinh 2IT} = \frac{x_2 + x_0}{x_1}$ can be computed in our scenario. Thus we can start from here and unwrap the hyperbolic sine function to try to calculate I .

$$\sinh 3IT + \sinh IT = c \sinh 2IT \quad (37)$$

$$\frac{e^{3IT} - e^{-3IT}}{2} + \frac{e^{IT} - e^{-IT}}{2} = c \cdot \frac{e^{2IT} - e^{-2IT}}{2} \quad (38)$$

Multiply by $2e^{3IT}$ on both sides:

$$e^{6IT} - 1 + e^{4IT} - e^{2IT} = ce^{5IT} - ce^{IT} \quad (39)$$

Using the change of variables $w = e^{IT}$, the problem becomes finding the roots of a sixth degree polynomial:

$$w^6 - cw^5 + w^4 - w^2 + cw - 1 = 0 \quad (40)$$

In general, we don't expect an exact algebraic solution to polynomial equations of degree five or higher due to well-known results in abstract algebra. However, this particular polynomial can be analyzed further without resorting to numerical

techniques.

$$w^4(w^2 - cw + 1) - (w^2 - cw + 1) = 0 \quad (41)$$

$$(w^4 - 1)(w^2 - cw + 1) = 0 \quad (42)$$

$$(w^2 + 1)(w^2 - 1)(w^2 - cw + 1) = 0 \quad (43)$$

$$(w^2 + 1)(w + 1)(w - 1)(w^2 - cw + 1) = 0 \quad (44)$$

Going through each factor from left to right: $w^2 + 1 = 0$ and $w + 1 = 0$ have no real solutions since $w > 0$; $w - 1 = 0$ has a solution with $w = 1$, which implies $e^{IT} = 1$ and $I = 0$. This is a trivial solution so we reject it for our purposes.

Use the quadratic formula to solve $w^2 - cw + 1 = 0$. Thus, $w = \frac{c \pm \sqrt{c^2 - 4}}{2}$ provided $c^2 \geq 4$. The goal is to plug the solution w to get the intensity $I = \frac{1}{T} \ln w$ so we actually need $c^2 > 4$ to ensure $w > 0$. We will show this by manipulating inequalities.

First observe that $x_2 < x_1 < x_0$ since the X forces are undergoing attrition. Next, observe that counting in time intervals of length T , the X force losses in the first time period $[t_0, t_1]$ will be greater than in the next time period $[t_1, t_2]$ because the Y forces are also undergoing attrition and $\frac{dx}{dt} = -\beta y$. Intuitively, there are fewer Y forces to shoot at the X forces as the battle progresses. Thus, $x_0 - x_1 > x_1 - x_2$.

$$c = \frac{x_2 + x_0}{x_1} \quad (45)$$

$$c = \frac{x_2 + x_1 - x_1 + x_0}{x_1} \quad (46)$$

$$c = \frac{x_2 + x_1}{x_1} + \frac{x_0 - x_1}{x_1} \quad (47)$$

$$c > \frac{x_2 + x_1}{x_1} + \frac{x_1 - x_2}{x_1} = 2 \quad (48)$$

We have $c > 2$ and $c^2 > 4$ as desired.

It is easy to see that both $w = \frac{c \pm \sqrt{c^2 - 4}}{2} > 0$ and can thus be plugged into $I = \frac{1}{T} \ln w$. However, we need the log value to be positive to have interesting values of I . Thus, we need the inequality:

$$\frac{c \pm \sqrt{c^2 - 4}}{2} > 1 \quad (49)$$

$$c \pm \sqrt{c^2 - 4} > 2 \quad (50)$$

$$c > 2 \mp \sqrt{c^2 - 4} \quad (51)$$

$$c^2 > 4 \mp 4\sqrt{c^2 - 4} + c^2 - 4 \quad (52)$$

$$\mp 4\sqrt{c^2 - 4} < 0 \quad (53)$$

Reject $w = \frac{c - \sqrt{c^2 - 4}}{2}$ which led to the contradiction $4\sqrt{c^2 - 4} < 0$. Keep $w = \frac{c + \sqrt{c^2 - 4}}{2}$ to plug into $I = \frac{1}{T} \ln w$. The discussion above proves the following theorem:

Theorem 3.3. Given x_0 , x_1 and x_2 . Let $c = \frac{x_2 + x_0}{x_1}$. The intensity I can be found using this one-sided information:

$$I = \frac{1}{T} \ln \left(\frac{c + \sqrt{c^2 - 4}}{2} \right) \quad (54)$$

4 PRACTICAL CONSIDERATIONS

In this section we put the recurrence relation and invariant form to the test with actual combat data, note some difficulties with the data analysis, and suggest an improvement.

4.1 Battle of Iwo Jima Data

We explore the validity of our model using casualty data from the Battle of Iwo Jima (1945). Time series data gathered from the US side is well-documented, but corresponding data gathered from the Japanese side is not as clear given the nature and outcome of the battle. This setup suits our framework of combat analysis using only one-sided information. Furthermore, it is known that the Battle of Iwo Jima fits the Lanchester square law well. These aspects make Iwo Jima an ideal battle to study for our purposes.

Engel verified the Lanchester square law using data from the Battle of Iwo Jima (Engel, 1954). The data was sourced from official records compiled by the US Marine Corps and published in the book *The Iwo Jima Operation* by Morehouse (Morehouse, 1946). Samz commented on Engel's paper and suggested some of the numbers should be corrected, but these corrections did not overturn Engel's conclusions about the successful verification of the Lanchester square law (Samz, 1972).

In more recent years, Stymfal reexamined Engel's verification work for his Master's thesis at the Naval Postgraduate School and found the square law to be the best fit amongst several options tried (Stymfal, 2022). Stymfal's thesis also contains

a table of daily casualty figures sourced from Morehouse’s book, Figure 1. The table contains data from D-day (February 19, 1945) to D+35 day (March 26, 1945) when the battle was essentially over. There are some known typos and minor errors in this data set. For example, the cumulative total casualties for D+19 and D+21 are both reported to be 18,204 troops, which logically cannot both be true if the corresponding number for D+20 is a different figure (17,692). Similarly, the number of WIA (wounded in action) is reported to be 10,632 on D+12 and 10,556 on D+13, but we expect the number of wounded to be an increasing function.

The Daily Total column in Figure 1 counts the daily change including all the newly killed, wounded and missing in action (KIA, WIA, and MIA respectively) for that day. We will refer to these daily numbers as the “daily change” going forward.

Day	Date	KIA	WIA	MIA	Cumulative Total	Daily Total
D-day	19 Feb	76	1,080	5	1,161	1,161
D+1	20 Feb	264	1,562	481	3,055	1,894
D+2	21 Feb	426	2,116	355	3,969	919
D+3 and 4	22, 23 Feb	870	4,711	670	6,251	2,282
D+5	24 Feb	1,021	5,284	537	6,845	594
D+6	25 Feb	1,195	6,006	549	7,750	905
D+7	26 Feb	1,347	6,791	484	8,622	872
D+8	27 Feb	1,556	7,984	586	10,126	1,504
D+9	28 Feb	1,616	8,418	575	10,661	535
D+10	1 Mar	1,845	9,150	599	11,595	934
D+11	2 Mar	2,005	9,780	545	12,333	738
D+12	3 Mar	2,278	10,632	541	13,451	1,118
D+13	4 Mar	2,468	10,556	631	13,655	204
D+14	5 Mar	2,620	10,753	546	13,919	264
D+15	6 Mar	2,715	11,054	452	14,221	302
D+16	7 Mar	2,869	11,505	430	14,804	583
D+17	8 Mar	3,055	12,251	435	15,741	937
D+18	9 Mar	3,191	12,723	445	16,359	618
D+19	10 Mar	3,315	13,203	421	18,204	581
D+20	11 Mar	3,488	13,785	419	17,692	752
D+21	12 Mar	3,653	14,130	421	18,204	512
D+22	13 Mar	3,765	14,403	434	18,692	398
D+23	14 Mar	3,878	14,750	434	19,062	460
D+24	15 Mar	4,112	15,102	437	19,653	591
D+25	16 Mar	4,206	15,290	423	19,928	275
D+26	17 Mar	4,305	15,474	417	20,196	268
D+27	18 Mar	4,357	15,511	397	20,265	69
D+28	19 Mar	4,403	15,598	391	20,392	127
D+29	20 Mar	4,457	15,677	359	20,493	101
D+30	21 Mar	4,503	15,732	353	20,538	95
D+31	22 Mar	4,540	15,820	336	20,696	108
D+32	23 Mar	4,590	15,954	301	20,845	149
D+33	24 Mar	4,590	15,954	301	20,845	0
D+34	25 Mar	4,590	15,954	301	20,845	0
D+35	26 Mar	4,590	15,969	301	20,860	15

* Action Report, Task Force 51, Joint Expeditionary Forces.

Figure 1: Morehouse data

In this battle, US forces landed on Iwo Jima to attack the heavily fortified Japanese forces that prepared ahead of time for the landing. We can take the numbers of US forces landing on Iwo Jima on various days and combine that information with the daily change figures to produce the number of US forces on Iwo Jima on each day of the battle. Engel and Samz diverged at this point and used different

D+i day	New landing troops (Engel)	New landing troops (Samz)
0	54000	30000
1	0	1200
2	6000	6735
3	0	3626
4	0	5158
5	13000	13227
6	0	3054
7	0	3359
8	0	3180
9	0	1454
10	0	252

Table 1: US landing forces

landing figures for their analyses. We will use the convention of having the integer i represent D+ i day, where $0 \leq i \leq 35$.

Combining the landing data from Table 1 with the daily change in casualties data from Figure 1, we can produce the following Table 2 of US force levels for both Engel and Samz data.

4.2 Data Analysis

The recurrence relation from Theorem 2.2 will be used to calculate a theoretical figure for how many US troops are left after combat operations on D+ i day, i.e. x_i . These x_i values will be compared with the actual values derived from the Morehouse, Engel, Samz data listed in Table 2.

The recurrence uses previous values, but new landing forces were added to the mix on various days in the Engel and Samz data. In order to avoid complications in the calculations resulting from the addition of new troops, we will treat D+5 to be

D+i day	US troops (Engel)	US troops (Samz)
0	52839	28839
1	50945	28145
2	56026	33961
3 and 4	53744	40463
5	66150	53096
6	65245	55245
7	64373	57732
8	62869	59408
9	62334	60327
10	61400	59645
11	60662	58907
12	59544	57789
13	59340	57585
14	59076	57321
15	58774	57019
16	58191	56436
17	57254	55499
18	56636	54881
19	56055	54300
20	55303	53548
21	54791	53036
22	54393	52638
23	53933	52178
24	53342	51587
25	53067	51312
26	52799	51044
27	52730	50975
28	52603	50848
29	52502	50747
30	52407	50652
31	52299	50544
32	52150	50395
33	52150	50395
34	52150	50395
35	52135	50380

Table 2: US forces (Engel and Samz)

the first usable day for the Engel data, after the final 13,000 additional troops have landed. Similarly, we will treat D+10 to be the first usable day for the Samz data, after the final 252 additional troops have landed.

Three consecutive previous values are needed to start off the recurrence. Let's denote x_{j-3} , x_{j-2} and x_{j-1} to be the “ j -seed values”. Thus, using the j -seed values in the recurrence relation, the first calculated value is x_j . Let $x_{i,j}$ denote the x_i value computed after using j -seed values to start off the recurrence, for $i \geq j$. We interpret $x_{i,j}$ as an estimate of the US force levels at D+ i day with the recurrence relation in this notation:

$$x_{i,j} = \frac{x_{i-1,j}(x_{i-1,j} + x_{i-3,j})}{x_{i-2,j}} - x_{i-2,j} \quad \text{for } i \geq j \quad (55)$$

The first usable day is D+5 for the Engel data, so $j \geq 8$ in this case since x_5 , x_6 and x_7 are $j = 8$ seed values. Similarly, the first usable day is D+10 for the Samz data, so $j \geq 13$. Table 3 shows some calculated $x_{i,j}$ values for the Engel data.

We are interested in the relative errors $\epsilon_{i,j}$ when using $x_{i,j}$ to predict US force levels at D+ i with j -seed values for $i \geq j$. These relative errors are computed by:

$$\epsilon_{i,j} = \frac{x_{i,j} - \text{actual}}{\text{actual}} \quad (56)$$

where “actual” refers to the US force levels at D+ i according to Engel or Samz data (Table 2). Tables 4 and 5 show some relative errors using the Engel data.

The recurrence relation is quite sensitive to errors and long-term predictions of force levels are not recommended with this model. However, the data also suggests that short-term predictions are possible with the recurrence relation. So long as

D+i day	US troops	j = 8	9	10	11	12	13
5	66150						
6	65245						
7	64373						
8	62869	63533.6					
9	62334	62726.3	60747.8				
10	61400	61950.7	58030.1	62759.8			
11	60662	61206.4	54742.8	64152.8	60073.0		
12	59544	60493.1	50917.9	66534.7	58361.4	60117.6	
13	59340	59810.4	46593.2	69942.0	56276.3	59765.2	58053.0
14	59076	59158.0	41811.0	74427.4	53831.0	59603.5	56198.4
15	58774	58535.5	36618.4	80059.9	51041.0	59632.1	53991.7
16	58191	57942.6	31066.2	86926.4	47924.4	59851.1	51446.8
17	57254	57379.0	25209.1	95132.7	44501.0	60261.1	48579.6
18	56636	56844.4	19104.4	104805.3	40792.8	60863.5	45408.1
19	56055	56338.5	12812.2	116093.2	36823.4	61660.1	41952.1
20	55303	55861.2	6394.1	129170.5	32618.3	62653.6	38233.4
21	54791	55412.1	-86.7	144238.7	28204.5	63847.1	34275.2
22	54393	54991.1	-6566.6	161530.0	23610.1	65244.4	30102.2
23	53933	54597.8	-12982.1	181311.0	18864.6	66850.0	25740.7
24	53342	54232.2	-19270.1	203886.5	13998.3	68669.0	21217.9
25	53067	53894.0	-25368.9	229604.6	9042.4	70707.1	16562.3
26	52799	53583.0	-31218.7	258861.5	4028.7	72971.0	11802.8
27	52730	53299.2	-36761.9	292108.3	-1010.9	75467.9	6969.5
28	52603	53042.3	-41944.3	329857.3	-6044.0	78205.6	2092.5
29	52502	52812.3	-46714.8	372690.4	-11038.3	81193.0	-2797.7
30	52407	52608.9	-51026.7	421267.8	-15962.1	84439.5	-7670.3
31	52299	52432.2	-54837.7	476338.2	-20783.6	87955.6	-12494.8
32	52150	52282.0	-58110.2	538750.4	-25472.2	91752.5	-17241.1
33	52150	52158.2	-60812.3	609466.4	-29997.6	95842.3	-21879.4
34	52150	52060.8	-62917.3	689576.1	-34331.1	100238.0	-26380.6
35	52135	51989.7	-64404.5	780314.2	-38444.8	104953.7	-30716.6

Table 3: US force levels $x_{i,j}$ predicted by the recurrence model (Engel)

	j = 8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
i = 8	1.1%							
9	0.6%	-2.5%						
10	0.9%	-5.5%	2.2%					
11	0.9%	-9.8%	5.8%	-1.0%				
12	1.6%	-14.5%	11.7%	-2.0%	1.0%			
13	0.8%	-21.5%	17.9%	-5.2%	0.7%	-2.2%		
14	0.1%	-29.2%	26.0%	-8.9%	0.9%	-4.9%	1.6%	
15	-0.4%	-37.7%	36.2%	-13.2%	1.5%	-8.1%	4.9%	0.0%
16	-0.4%	-46.6%	49.4%	-17.6%	2.9%	-11.6%	10.4%	0.3%
17	0.2%	-56.0%	66.2%	-22.3%	5.3%	-15.2%	18.4%	1.2%
18	0.4%	-66.3%	85.1%	-28.0%	7.5%	-19.8%	27.9%	1.4%
19	0.5%	-77.1%	107.1%	-34.3%	10.0%	-25.2%	39.4%	1.4%
20	1.0%	-88.4%	133.6%	-41.0%	13.3%	-30.9%	53.8%	1.7%
21	1.1%	-100.2%	163.3%	-48.5%	16.5%	-37.4%	70.2%	1.4%
22	1.1%	-112.1%	197.0%	-56.6%	20.0%	-44.7%	89.2%	0.8%
23	1.2%	-124.1%	236.2%	-65.0%	24.0%	-52.3%	111.6%	0.2%
24	1.7%	-136.1%	282.2%	-73.8%	28.7%	-60.2%	138.3%	-0.2%
25	1.6%	-147.8%	332.7%	-83.0%	33.2%	-68.8%	167.7%	-1.4%
26	1.5%	-159.1%	390.3%	-92.4%	38.2%	-77.6%	201.5%	-2.7%
27	1.1%	-169.7%	454.0%	-101.9%	43.1%	-86.8%	238.9%	-4.4%
28	0.8%	-179.7%	527.1%	-111.5%	48.7%	-96.0%	282.2%	-6.2%
29	0.6%	-189.0%	609.9%	-121.0%	54.6%	-105.3%	331.2%	-8.1%
30	0.4%	-197.4%	703.8%	-130.5%	61.1%	-114.6%	387.1%	-10.1%
31	0.3%	-204.9%	810.8%	-139.7%	68.2%	-123.9%	450.8%	-12.2%
32	0.3%	-211.4%	933.1%	-148.8%	75.9%	-133.1%	523.7%	-14.4%
33	0.0%	-216.6%	1068.7%	-157.5%	83.8%	-142.0%	604.6%	-16.8%
34	-0.2%	-220.6%	1222.3%	-165.8%	92.2%	-150.6%	696.3%	-19.4%
35	-0.3%	-223.5%	1396.7%	-173.7%	101.3%	-158.9%	800.5%	-22.0%

Table 4: Recurrence model, relative errors $\epsilon_{i,j}$ (Engel), I

	j = 16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23
i = 16	0.4%							
17	1.4%	0.1%						
18	1.8%	-0.8%	-1.2%					
19	2.0%	-2.3%	-3.1%	0.5%				
20	2.5%	-3.9%	-5.3%	1.9%	0.4%			
21	2.5%	-6.5%	-8.5%	3.4%	0.4%	-0.7%		
22	2.2%	-9.8%	-12.6%	5.4%	0.3%	-2.0%	0.2%	
23	2.0%	-13.5%	-17.2%	8.0%	0.3%	-3.5%	1.0%	0.3%
24	2.0%	-17.5%	-22.2%	11.7%	0.7%	-5.1%	2.5%	1.1%
25	1.2%	-22.4%	-28.2%	15.3%	0.5%	-7.5%	3.9%	1.5%
26	0.4%	-27.7%	-34.7%	19.6%	0.4%	-10.3%	5.7%	2.1%
27	-0.9%	-33.7%	-41.8%	24.1%	-0.1%	-13.7%	7.5%	2.6%
28	-2.1%	-40.0%	-49.3%	29.5%	-0.3%	-17.3%	10.0%	3.4%
29	-3.4%	-46.6%	-57.2%	35.6%	-0.6%	-21.2%	12.9%	4.3%
30	-4.8%	-53.5%	-65.4%	42.4%	-0.7%	-25.3%	16.3%	5.4%
31	-6.3%	-60.6%	-73.8%	50.1%	-0.9%	-29.7%	20.3%	6.9%
32	-7.8%	-68.0%	-82.4%	58.8%	-0.8%	-34.3%	24.8%	8.6%
33	-9.5%	-75.5%	-91.1%	67.9%	-1.0%	-39.3%	29.6%	10.2%
34	-11.4%	-83.3%	-99.9%	78.0%	-1.1%	-44.4%	35.0%	12.1%
35	-13.3%	-91.0%	-108.8%	89.1%	-1.1%	-49.7%	40.9%	14.2%

Table 5: Recurrence model, relative errors $\epsilon_{i,j}$ (Engel), II

n	Engel	Samz
1	28/28 = 100.0%	23/23 = 100.0%
2	22/27 = 81.5%	19/22 = 86.4%
3	17/26 = 65.4%	14/21 = 66.7%
4	12/25 = 48.0%	10/20 = 50.0%

Table 6: Accuracy of the recurrence model, $M = 3\%$ max relative error

the calculations are not used for too many time steps (in our case, days), then the relative errors were small enough to provide some useful information.

If we fix an arbitrary specification of falling within a max of $M = 3\%$ relative error to be a useful prediction, then we can look at how many j values can successfully meet that criterion in predicting what happens from $D+j$ day up to $D+(j+n-1)$ day. This would measure how accurate the model is for an n -day future outlook, including what happened on $D+j$ as the first prediction based on j -seed values. Table 6 shows the percentages of the relevant j values which can meet this accuracy criterion for n -day predictions for both Engel and Samz data.

The model can largely provide decent estimates if used for around, say, one to two time steps (days) forward based on the Battle of Iwo Jima data. Over 80% of the relative errors stayed within the $M = 3\%$ max relative error spec in the short-term up to two days. These conclusions can be drawn from both the Engel and Samz data.

Sometimes the relative errors became quite large over time. This is perhaps due to the use of division in the recurrence relation. It is well-known that the division operation can cause significant issues when performing numerical analysis with computers.

4.3 Linear Simplification

We will apply some reasonable assumptions to simplify the math and get around some of the issues noted in the recurrence relation data analysis above. In particular, we will avoid using the division operation. From Corollary 2.3, we have:

$$\frac{x_k + x_{k-2}}{x_{k-1}} = \frac{\sinh 3IT + \sinh IT}{\sinh 2IT} \quad (57)$$

In most battles, the attrition rates α and β are very small values since they represent how many enemy soldiers can be eliminated per unit of time by each soldier on average. The product $\alpha\beta$ will be even smaller still and will usually be close to 0. As such, the intensity $I = \sqrt{\alpha\beta} \approx 0$ in realistic battles.

$$\frac{x_k + x_{k-2}}{x_{k-1}} = \lim_{I \rightarrow 0} \frac{\sinh 3IT + \sinh IT}{\sinh 2IT} = 2 \quad (58)$$

A little bit of algebra yields the recurrence relation:

$$x_k - 2x_{k-1} + x_{k-2} = 0 \quad \text{or} \quad x_k = 2x_{k-1} - x_{k-2} \quad \text{for } k \geq 2 \quad (59)$$

The characteristic equation is:

$$r^2 - 2r + 1 = 0 \quad (60)$$

There's a double root at $r = 1$ so the general solution is:

$$x_k = ar^k + bkr^k \quad (61)$$

$$x_k = a \cdot 1^k + bk \cdot 1^k \quad (62)$$

$$x_k = a + bk \quad (63)$$

Plugging $k = 0$, we get $a = x_0$. Plugging $k = 1$, we get $x_1 = x_0 + b$, so $b = x_1 - x_0$.

Hence the general solution is:

$$x_k = x_0 + k(x_1 - x_0) \quad \text{for } k \geq 2 \quad (64)$$

The recurrence relation from Theorem 2.2 thus reduces to a linear approximation under these simplifying assumptions about the intensity of the battle.

With x_{j-2} and x_{j-1} as the two j -seed values, we can use the following simplified recurrence relation to calculate $x_{i,j}$ to predict US force levels at $D+i$ day:

$$x_{i,j} = 2x_{i-1,j} - x_{i-2,j} \quad \text{for } i \geq j \quad (65)$$

For Engel data, $j \geq 7$ since $D+5$ is the first usable day with x_5 and x_6 as the $j = 7$ seed values. For Samz data, $j \geq 12$ since $D+10$ is the first usable day. Tables 7 and 8 show some relative errors $\epsilon_{i,j}$ using Engel data.

Overall, the relative errors when predicting US force levels with the simplified recurrence relation are significantly smaller than when using the original recurrence

	j = 7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
i = 7	-0.1%								
8	0.9%	1.0%							
9	0.3%	0.5%	-1.6%						
10	0.4%	0.6%	-2.5%	0.6%					
11	0.1%	0.4%	-3.8%	1.0%	-0.3%				
12	0.5%	0.8%	-4.5%	2.0%	0.0%	0.6%			
13	-0.7%	-0.3%	-6.7%	1.4%	-1.3%	-0.3%	-1.5%		
14	-1.8%	-1.4%	-8.9%	1.0%	-2.4%	-1.1%	-3.0%	0.1%	
15	-2.8%	-2.3%	-10.9%	0.6%	-3.5%	-1.8%	-4.4%	0.3%	0.1%
16	-3.4%	-2.9%	-12.6%	0.7%	-4.1%	-2.1%	-5.4%	0.9%	0.6%
17	-3.4%	-2.8%	-13.8%	1.4%	-4.2%	-1.8%	-5.8%	2.2%	1.8%
18	-4.0%	-3.3%	-15.6%	1.6%	-4.8%	-2.0%	-6.7%	3.0%	2.4%
19	-4.6%	-3.8%	-17.4%	1.7%	-5.5%	-2.3%	-7.7%	3.7%	3.0%
20	-4.9%	-4.1%	-19.0%	2.1%	-5.9%	-2.3%	-8.5%	4.7%	4.0%
21	-5.7%	-4.8%	-20.9%	2.0%	-6.7%	-2.8%	-9.7%	5.3%	4.4%
22	-6.7%	-5.7%	-23.1%	1.8%	-7.7%	-3.4%	-11.1%	5.7%	4.7%
23	-7.6%	-6.5%	-25.3%	1.7%	-8.7%	-3.9%	-12.4%	6.2%	5.1%
24	-8.2%	-7.1%	-27.3%	1.8%	-9.4%	-4.3%	-13.5%	7.0%	5.8%
25	-9.5%	-8.3%	-29.7%	1.3%	-10.7%	-5.2%	-15.2%	7.2%	5.9%
26	-10.7%	-9.5%	-32.2%	0.8%	-12.0%	-6.1%	-16.9%	7.4%	5.9%
27	-12.3%	-11.0%	-35.0%	0.0%	-13.7%	-7.4%	-18.9%	7.1%	5.5%
28	-13.8%	-12.4%	-37.7%	-0.8%	-15.2%	-8.5%	-20.8%	7.0%	5.3%
29	-15.4%	-13.9%	-40.4%	-1.7%	-16.9%	-9.8%	-22.8%	6.8%	5.0%
30	-16.9%	-15.4%	-43.2%	-2.5%	-18.5%	-11.0%	-24.8%	6.6%	4.7%
31	-18.5%	-16.9%	-45.9%	-3.3%	-20.1%	-12.2%	-26.8%	6.4%	4.4%
32	-20.0%	-18.4%	-48.7%	-4.1%	-21.7%	-13.4%	-28.7%	6.4%	4.2%
33	-21.7%	-20.0%	-51.5%	-5.1%	-23.5%	-14.8%	-30.8%	6.0%	3.7%
34	-23.5%	-21.7%	-54.4%	-6.1%	-25.2%	-16.2%	-33.0%	5.6%	3.2%
35	-25.2%	-23.4%	-57.3%	-7.1%	-27.0%	-17.6%	-35.1%	5.2%	2.7%

Table 7: Simplified recurrence model, relative errors $\epsilon_{i,j}$ (Engel), I

	j = 16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23
i = 16	0.5%							
17	1.6%	0.6%						
18	2.2%	0.7%	-0.6%					
19	2.7%	0.7%	-1.2%	-0.1%				
20	3.5%	1.0%	-1.6%	0.2%	0.3%			
21	4.0%	0.9%	-2.3%	0.0%	0.2%	-0.4%		
22	4.2%	0.6%	-3.4%	-0.4%	-0.1%	-1.1%	-0.2%	
23	4.5%	0.3%	-4.3%	-0.7%	-0.4%	-1.6%	-0.3%	0.1%
24	5.1%	0.3%	-5.0%	-0.8%	-0.4%	-2.0%	-0.2%	0.5%
25	5.1%	-0.2%	-6.2%	-1.4%	-0.9%	-2.9%	-0.6%	0.2%
26	5.0%	-0.8%	-7.5%	-2.1%	-1.5%	-3.8%	-1.1%	0.0%
27	4.6%	-1.8%	-9.2%	-3.1%	-2.5%	-5.1%	-1.9%	-0.6%
28	4.3%	-2.7%	-10.8%	-4.1%	-3.4%	-6.3%	-2.7%	-1.1%
29	3.9%	-3.6%	-12.4%	-5.1%	-4.3%	-7.6%	-3.4%	-1.7%
30	3.5%	-4.5%	-14.0%	-6.1%	-5.2%	-8.8%	-4.2%	-2.3%
31	3.1%	-5.5%	-15.6%	-7.1%	-6.1%	-10.1%	-5.0%	-2.8%
32	2.9%	-6.3%	-17.2%	-8.0%	-7.0%	-11.3%	-5.7%	-3.3%
33	2.3%	-7.4%	-19.0%	-9.2%	-8.1%	-12.7%	-6.7%	-4.1%
34	1.7%	-8.5%	-20.8%	-10.4%	-9.2%	-14.1%	-7.7%	-4.9%
35	1.1%	-9.6%	-22.5%	-11.5%	-10.3%	-15.6%	-8.7%	-5.6%

Table 8: Simplified recurrence model, relative errors $\epsilon_{i,j}$ (Engel), II

n	Engel	Samz
1	29/29 = 100.0%	23/24 = 100.0%
2	28/28 = 100.0%	22/23 = 95.7%
3	25/27 = 92.6%	21/22 = 95.5%
4	23/26 = 88.5%	19/21 = 90.5%
5	18/25 = 72.0%	14/20 = 70.0%
6	15/24 = 62.5%	12/19 = 63.2%

Table 9: Accuracy of the simplified recurrence model, $M = 3\%$ max relative error relation from Theorem 2.2. Short-term predictions are possible based on an accuracy analysis of Iwo Jima data, but long-term predictions are not recommended.

Suppose we want relative errors to fall within $M = 3\%$ max relative error. We can look at how many j values can successfully meet this criterion in predicting what happens from $D+j$ day up to $D+(j+n-1)$ day using j -seed values. Table 9 shows the percentages of the relevant j values which can meet this accuracy criterion for n -day predictions for both Engel and Samz data.

The simplified model can largely provide decent estimates if used for up to four time steps (days) forward based on the Battle of Iwo Jima data. Over 85% of the relative errors stayed within the $M = 3\%$ max relative error spec in the short-term up to four days. These conclusions can be drawn from both Engel and Samz data.

5 CONCLUSION

We've demonstrated using a recurrence relation that knowledge of friendly force levels at three moments in time was enough to theoretically determine the outcome of a battle governed by the dynamics of the Lanchester combat model. Depending

on only one-sided information in combat modeling is somewhat realistic since battles are often fought with imperfect or even no information about enemy force levels. The Lanchester combat model is rich enough mathematically to allow for many details to be garnered despite the fog of war.

However, theory is different from practice. There are limitations to our approach in this paper. The Lanchester combat model is assumed to be sound in our analysis, but the model itself has not always fit nicely with actual historical battle data (Johnson (1989), Lepingwell (1987)). Various phenomena such as suppression of fire are known to negatively affect the conclusions predicted by the Lanchester combat model.

The Lanchester combat model is continuous while the attrition of forces is discrete. If we only use integer figures in our calculations, then this restriction will introduce “errors” according to the Lanchester combat model with its continuous attrition figures. McCue convincingly argues that taking a stochastic or probabilistic approach is the right way to get around these flaws with the Lanchester model (McCue, 2020).

We tested our one-sided combat model using data from the Battle of Iwo Jima. It was found that the recurrence relation can help with short-term predictions of friendly force levels, but is not robust enough to make accurate long-term predictions in the real world. Introducing a reasonable assumption allowed us to develop a simpler recurrence relation which was an improvement at making short-term predictions, but once more failed to accurately make long-term predictions of friendly force levels in real world conditions.

In this paper, we introduced a novel approach in combat analysis and demonstrated proof of concept that some relatively accurate short-term predictions can be made using only one-sided combat information in the real world. There is still much work to be done to improve this new tool.

Lastly, further questions can be asked and explored about what other aspects of the battle can be determined from just one-sided information or from the generating function. Further work can also be done to try to improve the accuracy of the model when faced with real battle data. There is much potential future research to be done in this interesting topic of one-sided combat modeling and it is hoped that this paper will help lay the foundation.

6 ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Thank you to the anonymous reviewers of the earlier draft of this paper. This paper has been improved with the reviewers' suggestions.

This paper is lovingly dedicated to my wife, Yuefan Ji, and to our baby daughter, Anya Li, who was born when this research in the mathematics of war was also being created and written. This is Anya's birthday paper.

References

Engel, J. H. (1954). A verification of lanchester's law. *Journal of the Operations Research Society of America*, 2(2):163–171.

- Johnson, R. L. (1989). *Lanchester's Square Law in Theory and Practice*. School of Advanced Military Studies, Fort Leavenworth, KS.
- Lanchester, F. W. (1916). *Aircraft in Warfare: the Dawn of the Fourth Arm*. Constable, London.
- Lepingwell, J. W. R. (1987). The laws of combat? lanchester reexamined. *International Security*, 12(1):89–134.
- McCue, B. (2020). *Beyond Lanchester: Stochastic Granular Attrition Processes*. Military Operations Research Society.
- Morehouse, C. P. (1946). *The Iwo Jima Operation*. USMCR, Historical Division, Headquarters US Marine Corps.
- Przemieniecki, J. S. (2000). *Mathematical Methods in Defense Analyses*. American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics.
- Samz, R. W. (1972). Some comments on engel's "a verification of lanchester's law". *Operations Research*, 20(1):49–52.
- Stymfal, M. (2022). *Revisiting Engel's Verification of Lanchester's Square Law Using Battle of Iwo Jima Data*. Naval Postgraduate School, Monterey, CA.
- Taylor, J. G. (1980). *Lanchester-Type Models of Warfare, vol. 1 and 2*. Naval Postgraduate School, Monterey, CA.
- Washburn, A. and Kress, M. (2009). *Combat Modeling*. Springer.
- Wilf, H. S. (2006). *Generatingfunctionology*. A K Peters.